

Human Resources, Its Classification and Categorization

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Abstract: In this article I have tried to classify and categorize human resources in a spatial and temporal manner. The views of different scholars are synthesized into a new piece of knowledge. A sharp distinction has been made between the human resources and other resources. The classification of human resources has not been constant and kept evolving in a spatial and temporal manner. Human resource classifications usually are based upon job evaluations in a department. It is sometimes also associated with job profile and task assigned to a person in an organization. There are two distinct methods of categorizing a human resource and resource. Human resources are categorized and classified within a particular set up, whereas resources categorization and classification may or may not have any such foundations.

Key words: Resources; Human Resources, Categorization; Classification

Full text:

In simple terms, resource may be defined as the means of supplying human wants. It may be anything or product which is useful to man and society. Resources generally have two attributes utility and function ability. Resource is a useful material which has a function in relation to man, and its function ability differs from place to place and from time to time.

In a broader sense, resources are classified in three categories as follows by economists (Dlabay Burrow, 2015):-

1. Natural Resources.
2. Human Resources
3. Capital Resources

However, biologists have classified them in living and nonliving resources. The economical classification included land, labour, capital, and entrepreneurship (Arvanitis, 2015). Goods and services produced by human are also sometimes classified as resources, in addition to machinery and logistics for production.

Human resources are the people who make up the workforce of an organization, business sector, or economy (Wikipedia, 2015). *Human capital* is sometimes used synonymously with human resources. However, human capital is also referred as a knowledge and skill an individual possesses that may be used for economic growth. Some other varied terms are also used for human resources such as labour, personnel, or people.

A human-resources department of an organization performs human resource management, overseeing various aspects of employment, such as compliance with labour law and employment standards, administration of employee benefits, and some aspects of recruitment and dismissal (Heathfield, 2015). Generally the term 'resource' refers to the function or operation of a thing or

substance in attaining a given end or in satisfying human wants.

It is, therefore, clear that resources result from an interaction between man - who searches means to attain given ends of individual or social objectives and possesses the capacity to take advantage of opportunities - and something outside of man which is called nature.

In fact, there is an absolute relationship between man and nature in the concept of resources. It can be said that there are two aspects - Natural or Primary and Man-made or secondary - where former leads to the natural things that are free gifts on the surface or beneath the surface and the latter leads to man-made things that are called the resultant output from the interaction of man and nature. This resultant output becomes available for use by man as a result of improvements made by him in nature. These improvements in natural gifts are called natural - cultural resources. But in bringing these improvements in natural gifts man applies his knowledge, skills/ Physical and mental capacity, spiritual strength and these are called the ingredients of human resources.

However, human resources are not only those which are organized and part of the economy as formalized. There is a big human resources even outside the economy still unorganized. Bringing them in the economy or organizing them would what the government in India has been gearing up mainly after globalization, privatization, and democratization.

There are seven major classified activities of human resources management, such as payroll, benefits, recruitment, training, employee services, community initiative, health and safety (Mooney, 2015). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has emerged as one of the major HR activities after the Companies Act, 2013.

Different thinkers have classified resources in their own ways. Some have emphasized temporal aspect, some have emphasized physical aspect and some others have

emphasized utilization aspect of resources. *Ritter* describes that resources are of three kind's natural resources, manmade resources and human resources.

Peach and Constantin classified resources into (a) tangible things - coal, iron, petroleum, copper, etc., (b) intangible or invisible things - such as health, social harmony, wise policies, knowledge, freedom, etc. He has further classified resources into land, capital and labour as the factors of production, and arrived at the conclusion that the trinity of natural, cultural and human aspects provide resource ship where the importance of human resources is obviously more crucial.

Harbison has also classified resources into natural, cultural and human as the factors of production. Both natural and cultural resources are a passive factor, whereas human resources are active factors of production who accumulate capital (cultural things), exploit natural resources, build social, economic and political organizations and carry forward national development.

Paterson suggested a simple classification of resources into two (a) physical resources (natural endowments 5 and (b) human resources (technological resources). But the other two - (c) population and (d) standard of living - are according to him, as a matter of fact, the measurement of interaction of resources. He holds that the existence of physical resources is independent of the action of man. Though man can use and reissues them and reduce their 'quality and quantity, but cannot affect their fundamental distribution which is an outcome of geological accident, position on the sphere, or age long physical process.

Spatial and Temporal Resources

Any consideration of resources of any kind would be meaningless if it is not supported by a spatiality and temporality. Resources may be available at one place at a particular time or other places at other particular time. The occurrence of resources doe suffered from a degree of spatial and temporal factors.

Generally, these three words have a wide or vague meaning, tor convenience of study, their definitions should be compartmentalized to a certain extent. Resources may be material or anything that satisfies human wants. Space means extent or area sufficient for some purposes. Tine means indefinite continuous duration regarded as that in which the sequence of events takes place, or a particular period indicated or characterized in some way. They differ in their meaning as much as they differ in their role of action in the development of a culture or a society. In spite of this, it is man, as a resource, who explores, investigates, exploits and accumulates natural endowment in space and time and in this process, he contributes his labour, mental and physical capacity with the aid, advice and consent of nature,.

It becomes essential to know the relations of resources, space, and time while discussing the concept of human

resources in the balance of the physical environment. There is an inalienable relation of resources with spatial - temporal system. Resources are unevenly distributed over the surface, beneath the surface.

These resources change from unusable form in useable form. In this changing process man causes the ecological balance of imbalance by exploiting natural endowments through time in the space or in physical Environment. In this way human resources are vital and most potent agent and make a difference in the pattern-of resources in the space and time.

Indeed, the concept of resources, space, and time includes the distribution of resources in space and its utilization or exploitation of human resources through time and qualifies for further explanation. The chart given below tries to clarify the Time is also a common element for all types of resources. - It is mainly related to use, exploration, exploitation, and growth of natural, human and cultural resources within a certain period of time. Tine includes past, present and future in which man 4s a resource played, plays and will play a vital role in the production and development of social goods. In transforming physical environments into cultural one man takes Space is common element of natural, human and cultural resources. In space, the distribution of all these resources is found. But the distribution of these resources are uneven on the earth's surface, over the earth's surface and beneath the earth surface. Space shows areal differentiation or variation in the Include land, mineral, famine, forest, water and other resources which are free gift on the surface or beneath the surface (*Shodhganga*, 2015).

Further resources can be classified into two categories of human resources and cultural resources. Human resources include the knowledge, skills, physical and mental capacity, etc., inherited actually or potentially in all people of under working age. The cultural resources included, a Joint product of man and nature. Include different types of cultural landscape.

Human Resources:

Harbison, has considered human resources as the wealth of nations. According to him "Human resources are the energies, skills, talent, and knowledge of people, which are, or which potentially can or should be, applied to the production of goods or the rendering of useful services". He has emphasized that man in relation to the world of work can be expressed in terms of the level of development, and the effectiveness of the utilization of human energies, skills, knowledge in all kinds of services for the social, political, cultural, and economic development of nations (*Harbison*, 1973).

Mehta has envisaged human resources in terms of human capital and defined it as the "sum total of the knowledge, skills, and aptitudes of the people, inhabiting the country. In a broader sense, it includes the initiative,

resourcefulness, capacity for sustained work, right values, interests and attitudes, and other human qualities conducive to higher output and accelerated economic 'growth'. Visualizing importance of human resource she has emphasized that a region having the largest population is not the richest in human resources or human capital, but the quality of working capacity of the people should be taken into consideration.

Human resource can be defined as "as the skills, knowledge and capacities of all people actually or potentially available for the economic and social development of their communities or countries." (UN, 1963).

Mamoria has used the term manpower as synonymous to human resources and holds that the phrase manpower was widely used in the past. According to him human resources are "the total knowledge, skills, creative abilities, talents, and aptitudes of an organization's workforce as well as the value, attitudes of an individual involved.... It is the sum total of inherent abilities, acquired knowledge and skills represented by the talents and aptitudes of the employed persons".

Ttakubasuskas and Palomba have considered human resources in terms of human capital and say "our human resources are, of course, the people who live in a nation." *Marx* called manpower as labour power and held that "by labour-power or capacity for labour is to be understood the aggregate of those mental and physical capacities, existing in a human being, which he exercises whenever he produces a use value of any description,"

Rosenbrock has defined human resources as "the skills and abilities of people," which are needed in the production process. From the above definitions, it is obvious that human resources are the qualities not quantities of man, but the exclusion of these qualities from the quantities is not justifiable. Here the word quality or qualities do not have meaning at all if it is excluded from quantities because quality signifies anything, whether it is in material or in abstract form which has some qualities and these become useful for satisfying human or social wants® For example, 'Minerals*' - are material which has different types of qualities and these qualities become useful after extracting and processing and ultimately they satisfy human or social wants. In the same way a human is materialized and quantified who inherit different types of qualities (in the form of power, capacity, energy, knowledge and different types of skills, etc.,) which are useful and required or to be required in the production of anything that satisfy human or social wants. But to measure these qualities is very difficult and they are always measured indirectly (in unit), not directly, counting the heads of the persons inhabiting the area as the qualities are inherited in individuals. One problem arises here is that some people, particularly from the discipline of economics, consider human resources or

manpower, consisting of only those persons who are between the ages of 15 to 59 years, who are gainfully employed in social production. They exclude children under 14 years old, persons of 60 years and above, full time students, women doing household duties, lunatics, criminals, unemployable persons and persons who are permanently unemployed.. Their concept is based on economic terms and laws*. According to law, child labour is not allowed in any industrial activities so is the case with retired persons.

But some from the same discipline and thinkers from other disciplines, particularly geographers consider the whole population of a region as human resources because all people inherit particular qualities (actual or potential) that, are used and are to be used in the production of use value of any description for satisfying human or social wants. It is also because of the fact that, human resources are considered as qualities that are inherent in human beings. So it does not sound proper that the persons between the ages of 15 - 59 years inherit such qualities and children, persons of 60 years and above and other unemployed persons are devoid of these qualities.

As a matter of fact, all people inherit different types of qualities. The only difference is that, employed persons contribute their skills, energies, capacities, knowledge, etc. in producing social goods for economic and social development. Children, the aged and the unemployed do not make such contribution for lack of opportunities. But if they are employed in different activities, they also produce social goods and services.

The type and quality of production, however, may differ according to their varying abilities. It is, therefore, argued that in the concept of human resources, all people (working age, over working age and under working age) should be included except the unemployable persons who may not work and may harm in production processes. But for doing justice, the children under 14 years who are under working age group should be provided schooling for Human Resource Development (HRD) for their future utilization the people of working age groups who are unemployed should be provided jobs and training for better utilization and persons of 60 years and above should be utilized as far as they wish to work taking care of their health.

Therefore, from this point of view 'Human Resources' are the sum total of knowledge, skills, energies, creative abilities, talents, physical or mental capacity for sustained work and other human qualities inherent in all people actually or potentially available which they exercise - or may exercise whenever they produce or may produce VA use value of any description for satisfying social needs.

Human Resources Classification:

'Classification implies' grouping together of persons or things on the basis of some common essential characteristics. In personnel administration, classification

means grouping together of posts into broad classes. On the basis of responsibilities. The classification plan places much emphasis on the position, its duties, responsibilities and qualification. Thus, a position may be defined as a specific office consisting of certain duties and responsibilities. The posts to which similar duties and responsibilities are attached are put into one class, regardless of the department in which they actually exist.

There is no unanimity among scholars over the classification of human resources and various approaches have been adopted in this process. *Batra* has emphasized the importance of skills embodied in individuals and on this basis human resources have been classified into three categories:

(1) High level manpower with critical skills and competence. This group includes such occupations, as doctors, physicians, metallurgists, chemists, biologists, educators, mechanists, civil and electrical engineers, administrators in private firms, public enterprises, government agencies, and educational institutions.

(2) Technicians - include the traditional. Occupations of draftsmen and surveyors, testing technicians, dental, medical and biological technicians, radio operators and communication technicians, etc.

(3) Skilled occupations - this group includes carpenters, brick masons, mechanists, die-makers, photo engravers, loom fixers, molders, boiler makers and many others.

Jakubasuskas and Palomba have given importance to quality, efforts and coordination of labour force and divided human resources into two heads {"Labour (manpower) and managerial skills."}

Agarwal has emphasized two points about a worker. The first is "what skill has he acquired?" that is related to education and the second is, "what work does he do?" that is related to occupation. Further, he emphasized that a specification of manpower categories could be done on either of the two bases indicated above.

Manpower categories specified by different organizations are based on the criterion of education and occupation, but they did not mention any other category in agricultural sectors. They specified categories only in non-agricultural sectors to the exclusion of others, particularly of the rural sector of the economy.

Yegnaraman on the other hand has given a classification of rural manpower. He adopted a criterion of occupation used in the National Classification of Occupation (N.C.O.) for categorizing the manpower in rural Meerut District.

Categories of Manpower

1. Professional, Technical and Related workers.
- 2 Administrative, Executive and Managerial workers.
3. Clerical and Related workers.

4. Sales workers,

5. Farmers, Fishermen, Hunters, Loggers and Related workers.

6. Miners, Quarryman and Related workers.

7. Workers in Transport and Communication Occupation.

8. Craftsmen, Production Process workers and Laborers not elsewhere classified.

9. Service, Sport and Recreation workers.

10. Workers not classifiable by Occupations.

This classification does not give a clear picture of workers engaged in household industries, construction process, etc. To make the classification comprehensive and applicable also to the rural sector of the economy with which the present work is concerned, human resources (both sexes) can be classified on the basis of educational attainment, economic activities or occupation, hours worked in a year, utilization, age etc. The details regarding these aspects are given in the methods of classification.

Means of Production and Human Resources

Various scholars have considered human resources as nation's wealth, asset, capital, input, consumption good and investment good etc. in their own ways, -but all the terms signify almost the same meaning and all are considered collectively as a factor of production. *Harbison* has considered human resources as the wealth of a nation which accumulate, exploited natural resources and build social, economic, political organizations for the development of the nation (*Harbison, 1973*).

Desatnic has emphasized the importance of human resources and held that the human resources are one of the most valuable -assets of a company. *Mehta* has used the term 'Human Capital' in place of human resources and laid emphasis on the formation of it through education, training, etc. Further, he has also stated that there is controversy among the scholars on the question - whether human resources should be treated as 'Capital'. *Hug* has emphasized that human capital is an active agent of economic growth# He has stated the quality of labour input as human capital that can be developed through schooling, training, etc. He has also stated that "capital once created is a free good in the sense that its use by one individual does not diminish its availability to others. Intellectual capital is both a part and product of investment in human capital and an important input in the production of new physical capital through technological change." *Upton* considers human resources as an input of production and it is indivisible input that cannot be separated from human beings. He has suggested the measurement of this input in terms of man-hours or man-days or man-years. Where ever or whenever man goes, this input goes with him. So human resources are inputs in the production of anything that satisfy human needs.

Joll, McKenna, McNabb and Shorey have taken education as an illustration of human resources and treated it as consumption and investment good in the production processes. They hold that "educational decisions are formulated in terms of the utility derived during the process of learning, the cost of provision and prices. Education is treated as an investment good within the traditional utility/profit-maximizing paradigm" e.g. students during the schooling period learn or gain knowledge, skills, etc. by their teachers. Here students consume the education and the teachers are treated as investors of human resources getting remuneration. It is, therefore, clear that human resources are - consumption and investment goods and they are consumed and invested in the process of production of anything. *Weisbroad and Hughes* have also treated education as both a consumption good and an investment good in the process of production. They have stated that "as per capita incomes grow a greater fraction of the population seeks higher education because of the consumption value it offers. As an investment good, education opens up job opportunities that persons without it cannot pursue." *Ebi Bio* has also considered human resources as an asset and in context of human resources development in developing nations, he has stated that "any development strategies and technology that will benefit these nations must utilize the greatest asset they possess - human resources - and develop them to find a solution to whatever problems that exist..."

From the above suggestions human resources or human capital is like material capital that is very important in economic and social development. In fact, there should be no controversy over treating human resources as wealth, capital, assets, consumption goods, investment good, input etc.

Factors influencing Human Resources:

Human resources are influenced by many factors, some factors promote the efficiency of workers while some others cause inefficiency which hinders the growth of the economy in a region. The following major factors may be considered to be influencing the efficiency of human resources:

1. Mental factor - This is the most important factor influencing the efficiency of human resources. Mental power is a very dynamic factor or element which may not be separated from man. It is the inherent element in man, which promotes his thinking and decision making capabilities. This directly affects the quality and quantity of human labour resources. If human resources are the main factors of production and thus of economic development, then the measures should be taken to develop the mental quality of people inhabiting the area through increased investment in human resources,

2. Physiological factors - are not less important, in influencing the quality of human resources.

All activities of man depend on his physical strength. If a person is physically misfit or weak in health, he may not be able to work properly and thus the development in all respects will either stop or will be hampered.

Streeten emphasizes the same point when he says, "A vigorous, healthy and skilled labour force is a more productive labour force and educated and healthy families tend to have fewer children." It is, therefore, essential to increase the health of laborer through provision of medical facilities, nutritious food, clean drinking water, adequate housing etc.

3. The psychological factors - are, also important in influencing human resources in a region. Attitude, aptitude, interest and others are psychological qualities of man which may be either encouraging or discouraging. If they are encouraging, they introduce a positive element in the efficiency of resource utilization, but they are discouraging they introduce a negative element and the efficiency of resource utilization goes down.

4. Organizational factors - also affect human resources in a variety of ways. Organization is one of the most important elements in the production of social commodities and it gives birth to induce, incentives and benefits. For the better organization, training, promotion, contest, professional insights and skilled knowledge should be taken into account. The organization should also create such environment, that there may be an increase in their mutual contact.

5. Competitive and non-competitive factors - are very influential in the firms or organizations where human resources are working. Competitive behavior encourages the labour inputs in production processes while non-competitive behavior discourages them and brings resistance to the development of a regional economy

6. Future prospects - also influence labour power resources in the production process. If workers have the prospect of future opportunities like, increment in wage, salary, promotion of posts or their amenities, then workers will take interest in their work. Similarly, if an agriculturist has the prospect of higher profits over his produce, he is encouraged to put his best in the process-

7. Cultural factors « play also effective role in influencing human resources of a region. Culture permits man to imitate nature, to improve on nature. It enables man to create new substances nowhere found in nature. Culture gives man the power to release energies not available in nature. It affects the most intimate of human moves, those governing reproduction.

8. Technology and the Arts - are the important factors which influence human resources and human resources affects production processes in the same way.

There is a good correlation of human resources and technology. Human resources are very much influenced by technical machine and tools. Technology has reduced

the labour value to some extent, increasing the tempo of labour power. But to handle the technical tools human resources should be educated and trained.

Technical arts render more effective man's productive efforts. According to *Peach and Constantin*, "arts designed to enlarge human capacity, raise human efficiency, and thus promote the economy of human energy.'

9. Physical factors - are very influential which mold the human resources in a particular region, physical factors include the effects of temperature, rainfall, humidity relief features and other elements of the natural environment. The qualities of man will be better where the natural environment is congenial to him and will be more active than that of the other uncongenial environment. For example, the people of Punjab are more energetic and hardworking than that of other states of India. They produce better yield than others. It is the physical environment that affects considerably the human resources of a region.

10. Economic factors - also have an influence on human resources and both are closely associated-

The people who are economically well, inherit better human resources. The person who is poor, is always poor in human resources. The poor people may not develop their education, physical and mental capacity and other skills, but richer people have better opportunities to develop, their capabilities.

11. Social factors - equally influence the efficiency of human resources. The development of human resources largely depends on the social environment in which they are nurtured. For example, the tribal people are still undeveloped because they suffer from a plethora of social deprivations which hold them down in their attempts to forge ahead in the race of economic wellbeing and technical skill. This is a qualitative sense, keeps them at a disadvantage in the level of human resources.

Problems of Human Resources Development;

Problems always stand against any type of development process. Here our concern is to see what are the problems which stand in the way of the development of human resources? In addition, how far and in what ways they diminish the efficiency of human power. This type of understanding would help us in applying the remedial measures, thereby improving the human resources both qualitatively and quantitatively. One of the major problems of human resources development is related to the number and distribution of people. They may be more than the area and the economy can support. One of the inevitable results of this over population will be that a considerable section of the human resources will remain unskilled and underdeveloped. This would result in gross inequalities in income distribution, asymmetries in political and social power distribution and a discriminating division of labour in the economic sector.

Unequal distribution of population within the territorial limit of a nation would also result in inequality of opportunities and consequent disparity in their development.

It is increasingly felt that the quality of human resources plays a very significant role in the development of rural and urban economy because economic development depends ultimately on the advance of knowledge and the expansion of education among all classes of the society. The spread of education is the most potent single factor of development. Lack of proper education works as a major constraint in the development of human resource potential.

Scarcity of technical and professional skills is another problem which hinders proper utilization of human resources. Only 13 per cent of the total human resources of the study area are skilled and have technical and professional knowledge. It is quite unsatisfactory from the point of view of qualitative development of human resources of the area. Technical/professional and skilled manpower is high level human resources which break the vicious circle of the economic growth. For the development or growth in rural economy this type of human resources is of utmost importance.

A general lack of work ethics is a serious problem under the existing Indian condition. In most cases the workers do not fit in the labour and skill required in their particular jobs. They are not sincere to their jobs. This is in sharp contrast to the Japanese workers whose sincerity and devotion to duty have become an essential part of their national trait.

Lack of this trait in under Indian conditions may be due to peculiar socio-cultural milieu in which the Indian work function - Lack of job satisfaction, lack of promotional avenues# lack of work appreciation of high-ups in the hierarchy# inadequate remuneration# and sometimes unnecessarily high job security. Under these conditions the productivity of the Indian worker in general# does not reach the optimum,

Child labour utilization is another problem which creates a long term problems regarding the quality of human resources. Utilization of child labour interrupts with the proper growth of the human resource potentials. This is like plucking off of a fruit before it is mature and ripe for use. This reduces the margin of profit for the grower, similarly, the use of child labour deprives the society of its future potentials. Children should be provided with the facilities of schooling and proper upkeep... to qualify them as a better human resource after their entry into the working age group.

Hygienic problem is also a problem of human resources which is related to health. In the development and utilization of human resources, health factor is very influential. The quality of manpower depends to a very great extent on the health status of the people. A

physically sound and healthy man works harder and more efficiently than a person physically weak and unhealthy. Health status increases the working capacity of the worker and it depends on the amenities s available to him. Under the existing Indian condition, the general health condition of the worker is much below optimum, rather poor, which adversely affects the functionality of the human resources. Unemployment of human resources is another problem.

Malhotra and Minocha have also emphasized that "human capital deteriorates when it is idle because unemployment impair skills that workers had acquired. This results generally due to excess of hands over available jobs. This results into large wastage of human materials at all levels. Sometimes jobs may be available, but the available manpower may not be having the requisite qualification or skill. This is due to lack of proper planning of educational expenditure. Then, there is the problem of underutilization of human resources. Lack of proper and efficient utilization of the available manpower stands in the way of adequate development of human resources. There are ample cases in which persons with high educational qualification and greater technical or professional skills are provided with jobs requiring lower education or skills.

This leads to job dissatisfaction as well as to wastage of human resources, we may say, this is a misuse of human resources.

Over utilization is also a problem pertaining to human resources. By over utilization is meant to engage the worker for more than eight hours of requisite working period. It does not promote capacity performance on the part of the working people. Contrary to it, this situation creates anxiety and frustration for many people. It has a debilitating influence in the long run. Over utilization of human resources may be due to poverty of the workers and excess work taken by the employer in any sector of the economy. The former relates to the workers who work willingly for earning wages and raising their living standard, whereas the latter is related to the employers who takes their labour forcibly to enhance their profits. This type of utilization may reduce the physical and

mental working capacity of the worker. They treat the worker as an object devoid of any feeling. In the words of Smith, "the dehumanized state of the slave is the ultimate example of treating people as objects." Over utilization is the process of dehumanizing people in the society and reducing them to the status of slavery*. This process reduces the capacity of the human labour in social production and cut short the period of their productivity.

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